

Modeling Collaboratory for Subduction - Draft integration section for the Fall 2021 SZ4D report

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This is the revised version of an MCS Integration section for the draft SZ4D report based on the efforts of the MCS RCN. You are welcome to comment on this draft, and/or fill out our feedback form at: <https://forms.gle/sND8kwpFHNGYfrX66>

Modeling Collaboratory for Subduction

The Modeling Collaboratory for Subduction (MCS) is a novel community- and model-building effort to advance subduction zone science. It was envisioned in the Boise Subduction Zone Observatories report (McGuire et al., 2017), and this chapter highlights the key points that have arisen from broad community discussions as part of the NSF-funded MCS Research Collaboration Network (RCN) in operation since 2018. The MCS RCN led to a series of community workshop discussions, summarized in detailed workshop reports at <https://www.sz4dmcs.org/> (Wada et al., 2019; Dunham et al., 2020; Wada & Karlstrom, 2020; Gonnermann et al., 2021). Additional workshops are scheduled for the remainder of 2021, and results from all of these MCS RCN efforts will be synthesized in a separate MCS report by the end of 2021.

The objective of the MCS is to create new kinds of physics-based models for earthquake and volcano-related hazards at subduction zones and apply them to understand fundamental processes, guide instrumentation deployments, interpret observations, and assess hazards (**Figure MCS-1**). Specifically, the MCS would be built around the following guiding questions:

- How do we construct models that link subduction zone state and long-term margin evolution to the character and probability of event occurrence?
- How can we best integrate observational constraints into models, while simultaneously using models to define optimal observational strategies (e.g., to reduce uncertainties)?
- How can we build physics-based, predictive models for volcano, earthquake, and geomorphic systems that couple across time and space?
- How can we build a diverse and equitable community of scholars?

At a more granular level, the MCS will work toward addressing the key science questions posed by the SZ4D working groups. All three working groups explicitly highlight modeling as an important tool in addressing their science objectives. For example, the Landscapes & Seascapes (L&S) working group argues that a new generation of coupled models that incorporate elastic and inelastic deformation at short and long timescales, surface processes, and fluid flow are required to simulate active processes in the forearc of subduction zones. Similarly, the Faulting and Earthquake Cycles (FEC) working group calls for the development of coupled simulations that connect regional models of stress and deformation, faulting, earthquake sequences, and aseismic slip to study megathrust rupture dynamics and resulting tsunamigenic

potential. Lastly, the Magmatic Drivers of Eruption (MDE) working group highlights the need for data assimilation in models of the magmatic-volcanic system in order to investigate magma migration processes that can lead to actionable hazard forecasts for volcanic eruptions. Thus, the need for physics-based modeling facilitated by the MCS is woven directly into the fabric of the SZ4D science plan.

A key goal of the MCS is to integrate geodynamic modeling into the observational and laboratory efforts of SZ4D from the outset, rather than the more typical sequence in which modeling is used only after data collection. In this way, modeling will be employed not only for interpreting datasets but in the planning and design phase of observational deployments. As observational deployments come online, data streams will then be assimilated into models to assess the “state” of megathrust and volcanic systems. The MCS will employ adjoint models and physics-enabled machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches that fully leverage the new datasets being collected. In this way, we seek to arrive at a transformational change in how large-scale, Earth programs are conducted in general and to enhance what they can achieve in terms of advancing solid Earth systems science.

In the context of the MCS, “model building” is a means to validate new physical descriptions, make predictions based on simplified theoretical approaches, and develop numerical models that can be used to explore the role and interaction of fundamental processes in controlling system behavior (i.e., for the geodynamics-driven discovery of emergent phenomena). Numerical modeling can also be integrated with laboratory experiments to facilitate the up-scaling of laboratory data to large-scale natural systems.

In addition, the MSC seeks to build more complex, “applied,” and regionally “realistic” models that can fully assimilate both structural information (e.g., from geophysical imaging and geology) and time-dependent sensor data streams (e.g., from seismometers and geodetic sensors) from subduction zone observatories. One exciting new direction in this regard is the development of adjoint models based on full or reduced-order physical models, as well as physics-enabled machine learning techniques, the combination of which have the potential to inform real-time hazard assessments alongside more traditional inversions of multi-sensor data.

Such new approaches are needed to consistently interpret constraints on the general workings of earthquakes, volcanoes, and surface processes in subduction zones, to identify knowledge gaps in our physical models, and to define optimal observational strategies to reduce uncertainties. Eventually, the MCS will lead to the new fundamental science and operational tools that are needed for quantifying, and possibly forecasting, earthquake, tsunami, landslide, and volcanic hazards.

Besides scientific discovery, integration of a new kind of modeling effort into SZ4D and the wider solid Earth community has numerous additional benefits, from training and interdisciplinary workforce development, to increasing the return on investment of new instrumentation and observational efforts by means of optimal experimental design.

It is clear that subduction zones on Earth are diverse in terms of their tectonic setting and/or current stage within their volcanic or earthquake cycles. To advance subduction zone science, it is therefore imperative to integrate observations from different regional laboratories to arrive at a globally validated physical understanding. The MCS is envisioned as a new SZ4D facility that can serve to support the development of such a framework and provide a home for sustained interactions between modelers, experimentalists, and observationalists.

Figure MCS-1. *Digital Twin concept of a modular, building-block-based framework for physical modeling provided by the MCS to explore general physical processes and to digitally mirror regionally specific subduction zones, for example, to interpret real-time sensor data for system “state.” (left) Conductivity structure for Central America from Naif et al. (2015).*

This is crucial because we do not yet know how to assemble complete models of earthquakes and volcanoes. The MCS can provide the building blocks to test alternative physical descriptions and identify the most important processes in controlling system behavior. Moreover, the MCS can support global subduction zone research communities, including the local stakeholders, as well as international and domestic observatories in different stages of their implementation, helping to support cross-disciplinary and cross-site collaborations. Crucially, model-based cross-validation is needed to quantitatively link insights from international infrastructure investments to hazard and risk settings of domestic societal concern for the United States.

Further, while any successful study of subduction zones requires an appreciation of their geologic diversity, it also requires acknowledging the importance of fostering a diverse scientific community to perform these studies. Perhaps the greatest long-term opportunity presented by the MCS is to establish computational approaches as alternative entry pathways for underserved and underrepresented communities into the geosciences. Such efforts will complement more traditional training and community-building efforts to empower computational scientists with the interdisciplinary tools they need to be successful. Together with extensive, sustainable, equitable, and coordinated outreach and teaching efforts (e.g., to enhance quantitative literacy in K–12 students and undergraduates), the MCS and the computational geosciences, in general, can contribute greatly to efforts to build a better and more diverse community of geoscientists. This important theme is further explored in the Building Equity and Capacity with Geoscience (BECG) chapter, and the MCS will play a large contributing role in initiating and supporting belonging, accessibility, justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion (BAJEDI) efforts within SZ4D.

MCS DESIGN GOALS

To achieve these ambitious scientific and community goals for the MCS requires an extensive and continued effort in supporting computational geoscience. We need to create new pathways for discovery that are based on investments in human and computational infrastructure and that are supported over timescales longer than a typical grant cycle (**Figure MCS-2**).

MCS RCN reports are available for the community workshops on the Megathrust, Volcano, and Fluid Transport components of the subduction zone problem (<https://sz4dmcs.org>), with an additional implementation workshop planned for links with Landscapes & Seascapes in the fall of 2021. However, clear and common themes have already crystallized from these extensive community discussions among observationalists, experimentalists, and modelers.

Figure MCS-2. Immediate objectives and organizational components of the MCS within the SZ4D context and example partnerships within the wider community.

Specifically, in terms of its design goals, the community recommends that the MCS should:

- Support the sustained exchange between computational, observational, and laboratory subduction zone scientists within the SZ4D and the geodynamics community at large through workshops, hackathons, and shared model building.
- Support SZ4D operations through community structural model storage and serve as a repository for inverse and forward modeling and data analysis tools from all disciplines involved in SZ4D.
- Support both interdisciplinary subduction process-focused working groups, as well as groups studying specific regional laboratories and case histories, such as volcanic eruption and earthquake sequence scenarios.
- Support continued model and modeling framework tool development and benchmarking exercises, with a mix of centralized and distributed approaches, based on continuous community input and guidance, and supporting both community-based code development, as well centralized framework efforts (like tools and databases linking observables with transport properties).
- Support access to computing resources, empower scientists with different backgrounds and institutional support, and broaden and democratize participation in leading-edge, data-driven, high-performance and cloud computing within the solid Earth sciences.

While striving to achieve these goals, the MCS should be strategically guided by principles such as:

- Putting model component *verification* and benchmarking first, making sure that codes tackle the subsystem components involved in the coupled multi-scale, multi-physics problems correctly and efficiently.
- Studying interactions across scales and exploring coupled physical processes, while moving toward *validation* (i.e., making sure that the overall physical representations—the coupled subduction models—are the right ones). For this, the general framework has to be tested as widely as possible by the integration of different regional subduction zone settings and natural laboratories.
- Recognizing that a range of alternative, possibly competing, modeling approaches are needed and that, when possible and appropriate, support modular workflows made out of modular building blocks (**Figure MCS-1**) rather than a single “consensus” approach for how the physics of subduction should be modeled.
- Ensuring close collaboration between computational and applied math experts and domain scientists, as well as close exchange between modelers, experimentalists, and observationalists. The latter includes supporting modeling and model construction by observationalists, and appreciation of data analysis and laboratory experiments by modelers, in the spirit of empowering transdisciplinary research.
- Providing flexible, robust, well-documented, and efficient open-source codes with inherent consideration of multi-physics, cross-scale, adjoint approaches, and uncertainty quantification.
- Developing a range of codes with tutorials, cookbooks, and workflow examples to allow the use of models for both teaching and research applications.
- Embracing the guiding principles of open science and FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) data practices.
- Empowering the widest and most diverse representation of the community, equitable representation of all voices, and supporting active international collaboration.

In these efforts, the MCS is not operating in isolation, but is meant to serve as a science hub for SZ4D (**Figure MCS-2**) and beyond, providing the most versatile tools possible while driven by the goal to create physical models for subduction zone hazards. The MCS science objectives overlap with several agencies (NSF, USGS, NASA, NOAA) and community organizations (e.g., Community Surface Dynamics and Modeling System [CSDMS], and Computational Infrastructure for Geodynamics [CIG]), and existing and possible future earthquake centers in the United States. There are also clear links with a number of international partners, such as ChEESE, an initiative to bring cutting-edge solid Earth high-performance computing enabled codes closer to hazard applications.

On the training and capacity building side, SZ4D will be driven by a collective broader impact perspective, and the MCS can also usefully partner with efforts in terms of training pursued by organizations such as SAGE/GAGE, Cooperative Institute for Dynamic Earth Research (CIDER), CIG, and CSDMS.

Unlike the seismological or geodetic communities, supported by SAGE/GAGE, the computational solid Earth geosciences do not yet have a dedicated, comprehensive, and science-question independent computational infrastructure (e.g., “CAGE”) to rely on, but moving into such a future, there are many

mutually beneficial opportunities for partnership with efforts such as CIG or CSDMS. Their scope and capabilities are, however, distinct from the MCS, which is an unprecedented effort as discussed next in terms of implementation examples.

DRAFT IMPLEMENTATION

Figure MCS-3 portrays a few specific examples for some of the MCS model building blocks. They would include fully verified component tools for subsystems that the MCS would immediately help develop by supporting community-driven developments, centralized programming efforts by MCS center personnel, and hybrid approaches such as working with programmers “on loan” to PIs outside the center. The focus here is on the challenging geodynamic modeling applications identified by the earthquake, volcano, and surface process communities within SZ4D as key first steps to take to accelerate science integration and model building.

These blocks could consist of smaller bricks of well-tested components. They could also subsequently be assembled into even more complex assemblies, such as for regional natural laboratories (**Figure MCS-3**), or reassembled for a range of related problems outside subduction zone science. While the overarching strategy of the MCS is to develop modular modeling blocks consisting of ideally interchangeable, smaller bricks (e.g., different solvers for a visco-elastic model with fluid flow), we recognize that full modularity and coupling of bricks may not be feasible or desirable for some problems, at least in the near term. Many of the multi-physics problems we seek to explore do indeed require what is known as “tight” coupling, for example, at the solver level, and hence dedicated, specialized, and highly optimized codes. In these situations, the brick-based approach may not be tractable, and we will instead focus on developing more specialized blocks (e.g., at the level of the examples in **Figure MCS-3**). However, for all development, we will make sure that those lead to well-benchmarked codes that are accessible to the community, not just for download but also by means of well-documented cookbooks and example applications.

Thermo-petrological magma dynamics (host rock + dike)	Visco-elastic earthquake cycle with fluid transport	Global, 3-D, thermal convection with two phase flow	Multi-physics, multi-scale forward modeling framework (Julia, FEniCS)
Coupled tectonics-surface processes	Complex physico-chemical fluid framework	Upscaling of granular mechanics and stochastic process models	Python/Jupyter notebook cookbooks and teaching modules
Physics-enabled machine learning for sensor data and forward models	Real-time data analysis support codes / workflows	Multi-constraint geophysical inversion toolbox	Multi-physics adjoint inverse framework (Julia, FEniCS)

Figure MCS-3. Example building blocks an MCS might develop to support fundamental and regionally applied subduction zone hazard modeling. Each block would include multiple bricks, for example, the visco-elastic earthquake cycle set might include fluid solver, solid solver, and friction solver bricks.

MCS COMPONENTS

Figure MCS-4 shows how the MCS infrastructure and capabilities can be compartmentalized to achieve the previously mentioned goals. To fully realize our objectives—advance integrative subduction zone science with a large footprint in capacity building; enhancing diversity; empowering a wider subset of the solid Earth community in the use of high-end HPC and cloud computing; and contributing to geoscience education from K–12 to college levels—requires these components and more.

Figure MCS- 4. Example capabilities as well as human and computational infrastructure components of an MCS.

At a minimum operational level, the MCS requires the following capabilities:

- Support for workshops, hackathons, and training for continued collaboration between observationalists, experimentalists, and modelers
- Repositories for models (time-independent geological and geophysical data) for SZ4D and other natural laboratories, as well as for primary and derived data product workflow
- Repositories for code documentation, cookbooks, and teaching material
- A dedicated program manager/coordinator
- A community-sourced and engaged science planning committee made up of modelers and observationalists

Such activities are crucial, and previous, long-term community efforts have shown, for example, that even the construction of community structural (e.g., seismic velocity, fault) models as well as automating and fully documenting secondary and tertiary data product workflows can be challenging. Existing expertise could be leveraged here, and collaborating with other community centers and workflow archiving efforts might suffice to make basic data and data product infrastructures operable.

However, to achieve a transformational advance, we must go beyond these basic capabilities and invest in continued model and community development. To achieve these more ambitious goals, the MCS requires:

- Support for multiple programmers (e.g., with HPC, applied math, visualization, database focus) at a central facility and make these individuals available to the community through a competitive grant process
- Issuing of subawards for distributed, but coordinated code development (outside of, or a dedicated component of any core SZ4D science program) or MCS needs to be supported by a long-term science plan and allocated program budget with competitive proposal review at NSF.

Only by providing these key pieces of infrastructure to the SZ4D community will the MCS be able to achieve the vision described above and go beyond prior community efforts in solid Earth computational sciences. Lastly, an ideal MCS would also include the following elements:

- Access to computing allocations, portals, and cloud workflow systems
- Support for a postdoc program in which postdocs reside with PIs, but benefit from being part of a cohort coordinated with the center, for example, by means of participating in yearly hackathons and workshops, as well as more sustained opportunities for training
- Support for competitive and inclusive graduate fellowships, with a focus on entraining new and underrepresented members to the geoscience community from diverse backgrounds

The components needed for the transformative advance described above can only be realized through sustained investment in a new computational facility. Such a facility would house a community code development team led by a group of computational scientists. An MCS office would facilitate community engagement throughout workshops, hackathons, postdoc and graduate fellowship programs, and DEI initiatives. Lastly, PI-driven science would be supported through a competitive grant process allowing individual researchers to both leverage the computational resources of the MCS and contribute to the development of new community codes.

We are at the cusp of achieving a new level of insight into subduction zone science and hazards, training the emerging next generation of computational subduction scientists, and elevating computational geoscience approaches to a true partnership with observational and laboratory approaches. Achieving this paradigm change requires bold investment and could be the beginning of a new area in solid Earth geoscience.

PHASING

What we can do right away: Start building a center, form a community-based planning process, hire programmers, start workshop and postdoc programs, and define and refine immediate code development tasks (in-center development, external grants to PIs, focus on open source and common standards, but not only community codes). Compile and assemble existing constraints from regional laboratories, assemble structural (static models). Compare those for key SZ4D sites with derived data products. Define specific regional sub-problems in coordination with FEC, LS, and MDE working groups, including modeling geared toward exploring optimal configurations for volcano and earthquake instrumentation based on existing and newly designed modeling codes. Use insights for experimental design (e.g. seismometer placement given asperity modeling; where/how to co-locate WG components). Assess community access to computing and training, work toward equitable participation with BECG.

Framework and codes supported after five years: Complete initial code development tasks. Develop a set of teaching and research codes and cookbooks. Initiate a summer school program. Train observationalists and laboratory scientists in code use and work on enhanced cookbook models. Refine codes depending on observationalist use. Complete storing house for inverse code and inverse frameworks. Reassess optimal solution strategies, focus on high-performance, cross-scale code development for adjoints and UQ. Complete first round of verification exercises. Define more ambitious benchmarks. Continue grant program to PIs and develop new code. Establish portals to run both forward and inverse models and hackathons and tutorials to broaden model use by non-specialists. Commence work on time-dependent adjoints and explore feeding real-time data to regionally adapted models using actual observatory data and synthetic tests. Assess tool useability and impact of training exercises. Reassess access to computing and portal/cloud strategy. Use modeling tools to refine hypotheses, identify knowledge gaps, and improve observational strategies.

Integration of real-time data streams (10 yr): Complete real-time tests for different earthquake and volcano settings. Quantify uncertainties for regional settings, and for general process models. Formalize cross-site validation. Assess the degree to which earthquake and volcano systems need to be modeled across spatio-temporal scales to assess state and provide eruption and rupture scenarios. Provide fully realized regional workflows, while continuing grant program to PIs and new code development. Reassess experimental and observational strategies to reduce uncertainties. Reassess capacity building and training efforts.

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